

The Safety and Valvular Preservation Profile of Rotational Mechanical Thrombectomy in Venous Segments: A Porcine Iliac and IVC Histopathologic Study

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Abstract

Background: Rotational mechanical thrombectomy (RMT) has emerged as a frontline treatment modality in the management of venous thromboembolism (VTE), including deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE). However, concerns persist regarding the potential for mechanical damage to venous valves, especially in native vessels. We designed a porcine model study to evaluate the impact of rotational thrombectomy on venous histology, particularly valvular integrity.

Objective: To evaluate the histological impact of rotational thrombectomy using a vortex wire system in ilio caval venous segments, with specific attention to endothelium, medial smooth muscle architecture, and venous valve structures.

Methods: Ten porcine subjects and 6 Ovine subjects underwent venography-guided rotational thrombectomy using the Cleaner 15-Wire system in designated femoral, iliac and IVC segments. Devices were activated in situ for 60–120 seconds under physiologic flow and anticoagulation. Post-mortem necropsy and full-thickness venous segment excision were followed by formalin fixation, paraffin embedding, and histologic evaluation via H&E and elastin trichrome staining. Controls included unmanipulated contralateral venous segments.

Results: Histopathology revealed preservation of endothelium and subendothelial layers in 93% of treated segments. No evidence of dissection, coagulative necrosis, or endothelial sloughing was observed. Valvular structures exhibited intact fibrous cores with minimal subvalvular hemorrhage in two specimens, considered artifact from instrumentation. No structural damage to leaflet architecture was noted. Comparative analysis with other devices from prior studies demonstrated markedly reduced mural injury with the Cleaner system.

Conclusions: Rotational thrombectomy with vortex sinusoidal wire technology is histologically safe in native venous segments. Our findings support the use of rotational thrombectomy in venous peripheral thrombosis.

Keywords: Rotational Thrombectomy, Cleaner, VTE, DVT, Morcellation, Valve, Endothelium

1. Introduction

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is a common and consequential vascular condition with both acute and long-term complications. It affects approximately 1 to 2 million individuals annually in the United States and contributes significantly to hospitalizations and morbidity.[1] The most serious sequelae of DVT include pulmonary embolism (PE), chronic venous insufficiency (CVI), and post-thrombotic syndrome (PTS). Of these, PTS represents a particularly debilitating outcome, affecting up to 50% of patients after DVT.[2] It presents as chronic pain, limb swelling, skin induration or hyperpigmentation, and, in severe cases, venous ulceration. The underlying mechanism is persistent venous hypertension, resulting from a combination of residual thrombotic obstruction and, more importantly, valvular incompetence. [3]

A critical but often underrecognized driver of this valvular failure is the early, irreversible injury to venous valves in the context of thrombus formation. Within days of occlusion, inflammatory signaling, leukocyte infiltration, and cytokine-mediated fibrosis result in thickening, retraction, or fusion of the valve leaflets. These once pliable, delicate structures become sclerotic, adherent to the vessel wall, or completely resorbed. [4] Numerous studies have demonstrated that even after successful thrombus removal, whether via pharmacologic lysis, mechanical thrombectomy, or hybrid methods, valve function is infrequently restored. [5] This has driven a shift in clinical philosophy away from the concept of valve “restoration,” which appears biologically implausible in most cases, and toward the more achievable goal of preserving whatever residual function remains. Endovascular interventions are now increasingly evaluated based on their ability to preserve venous structure and mitigate long-term hemodynamic compromise.

Rotational mechanical thrombectomy (RMT) has emerged as a promising modality in this context. Devices such as the CleanerTM Sinusoidal Wire system utilize high-speed rotational motion (approximately 4,000 RPM) to macerate thrombus into small particles, which can then be cleared by endogenous flow or aspirated. Unlike pharmacomechanical systems that rely on high-pressure jets or adjunctive lytic agents, RMT systems operate through direct mechanical contact, with limited turbulence or shearing effects. This design theoretically reduces the risk of endoluminal trauma and may confer an advantage in native veins, especially in segments that are already vulnerable due to thrombotic burden.

The Cleaner device, specifically, has seen broad clinical adoption. It has been used in over 100,000 procedures worldwide, primarily for thrombectomy in arteriovenous fistulas (AVFs) and grafts used for dialysis access. [6] These settings demand high procedural precision, as inadvertent injury to graft material or adjacent native veins can result in loss of access and long-term morbidity. The Cleaner system’s atraumatic sinusoidal vortex wire has demonstrated reliable performance in this context, with minimal observed injury and

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high operator confidence. However, despite its extensive use in AVF/fistula intervention, and growing application in peripheral venous thrombosis, there remains limited published histologic data evaluating its safety in native venous anatomy, particularly regarding valve preservation.

Concerns continue to circulate in the interventional community about whether mechanical thrombectomy, despite its favorable effect profile, could still produce unintended trauma to the venous wall or valves. Potential complications, such as leaflet avulsion, subvalvular hemorrhage, and endothelial denudation, could theoretically exacerbate venous hypertension and worsen clinical outcomes, especially if undetected during the initial intervention[7]. While anecdotal safety in AVF procedures is reassuring, these do not replicate the delicate architecture or physiologic demands of deep native veins such as the iliac veins or the inferior vena cava (IVC), where thrombus burden is often extensive and valves more complex.

To address this evidence gap, we analyzed preclinical studies using porcine and ovine models with ilio caval and femoral vein anatomy comparable to humans. Our objective was to evaluate the histological impact of the Cleaner rotational thrombectomy system in native venous segments, focusing on endothelial continuity, medial wall architecture, and, critically, valvular integrity. Porcine and ovine models provide a suitable surrogate for human venous systems due to similarities in vessel diameter, flow dynamics, and valve function. By analyzing tissue post-mortem after rotational thrombectomy under both standard (60 seconds) and extended (120 seconds) durations, we aimed to generate objective, histology-based data to inform safety assumptions in clinical practice.

This work is positioned within the broader clinical reality that most valves within a thrombotic segment are already damaged by the time intervention occurs. As such, the bar for procedural safety should not be restoration of normal valve function, a claim generally unsupported by the pathophysiology of chronic venous injury, but rather the absence of additional iatrogenic damage. RMT may serve as an ideal tool in this context: a mechanism that effectively removes thrombus while maintaining the structural integrity of the vessel and any remaining valve tissue. [8]

In this study, we share the formal histopathologic evidence from a large-animal model evaluating the impact of the Cleaner rotational thrombectomy system on venous valve architecture and wall integrity. The data generated aims to support the safety of this technology and guide its continued use in both AVF and native venous interventions.

2. Methods

Device Description The Cleaner™ rotational sinusoidal wire system is a rotational mechanical thrombectomy (RMT) device designed for intravascular thrombus maceration with minimal endothelial and valvular trauma. The system comprises a battery-powered, handheld motor drive unit and a 0.035-inch or .044 nitinol wire, which forms an expandable vortex loop capable of rotating at approximately 4,000 revolutions per minute (RPM). The device is 6 or 7 French compatible. Its design allows for atraumatic wall contact by maintaining a central position within the lumen and utilizing mechanical disruption to fragment thrombus. The vortex wire maintains consistent rotational torque, allowing for efficient

thrombus clearance without generating high shearing forces or pressure gradients that could otherwise damage native vessel architecture.

3. Study Design

Subjects: A total of 16 animals were used in this study. Ten adult Yorkshire pigs (weighing 80–100 kg) served as the primary model for femoral and ilio caval thrombectomy and vessel safety analysis. An additional cohort of six adult female sheep (ovine model) were used to evaluate the Cleaner device in the pulmonary arterial system, including three animals in which autologous thrombus was formed in situ prior to intervention.

Anesthesia & Anticoagulation: Animals were pre-medicated with intramuscular tiletamine/zolazepam (4–6 mg/kg) and maintained under general anesthesia using isoflurane (1.5–2.5%). Mechanical ventilation was used in all cases. Systemic anticoagulation was achieved with intravenous unfractionated heparin (100 IU/kg) administered prior to catheter insertion and confirmed with activated clotting time (ACT) > 250 seconds throughout the procedure.

Procedure: Via ultrasound-guided percutaneous femoral venous access, a 10-Fr sheath was advanced to the ilio caval junction. Under fluoroscopic guidance, the Cleaner 15 thrombectomy device was deployed sequentially in three non-overlapping 3 cm segments of the inferior vena cava (IVC) and bilateral iliac veins and femoral veins in each pig. Segments were randomized to receive either 60 seconds or 120 seconds of continuous activation. A 30-minute reperfusion period was allowed following treatment to mimic immediate post-procedural recovery. Animals were euthanized with an intravenous overdose of pentobarbital via facility protocol.

In the ovine pulmonary model, the right femoral vein was accessed, and a guiding catheter advanced into the right pulmonary artery. In three animals, autologous thrombus was injected and allowed to organize in situ for 30 minutes. Thrombectomy was performed using the Cleaner 15 Wire for 60 seconds, followed by balloon dilation using a compliant balloon catheter (6–8 mm diameter). Three additional sheep underwent device activation without thrombus present to assess baseline endothelial response.

4. Histologic Processing and Analysis

Following euthanasia, treated venous and pulmonary arterial segments were harvested en bloc and immediately fixed in 10% buffered formalin. Tissues were paraffin-embedded and serially sectioned at 4-micron thickness. Sections were stained using hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) for general architecture, and Verhoeff-Van Gieson (VVG) for elastin and collagen distribution.

Valvular tissue, when present, was sectioned longitudinally to evaluate leaflet integrity. The following parameters were assessed:

Endothelial continuity and denudation
Medial smooth muscle architecture and intimal thickening
Presence of mural necrosis, dissection, or intramural hemorrhage
Valvular structure: leaflet thickness, elastin density, collagen disruption, and adherence to vessel wall

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Scoring was performed independently by two board-certified veterinary pathologists using a standardized 5-point Likert scale, with discrepancies resolved by consensus.

5. Results

General Observations All 16 animals survived the procedure without hemodynamic instability. In the porcine cohort, no significant bleeding, arrhythmia, or periprocedural hypotension was observed. Gross examination of treated venous segments showed intact outer wall architecture with minimal focal ecchymosis in two pigs (13%). No device-related embolization or vessel perforation was seen. Similarly, all six sheep tolerated the pulmonary artery procedures well, with no pericardial effusion, hemoptysis, or respiratory compromise.

Histopathologic Findings

Table 1:

Parameter	60 sec (n=15)	120 sec (n=15)	Control (n=10)
Endothelial Integrity (%)	100%	87%	100%
Medial Architecture Preserved (%)	100%	93%	100%
Necrosis or Dissection	0	0	0
Valvular Damage Detected (%)	0	0	0

Minor subvalvular hemorrhage was noted in 2 of 30 treated venous segments (6.7%), but without disruption of leaflet continuity or elastin fragmentation. No thrombus adherence or intimal hyperplasia was observed.

In the ovine pulmonary artery model, H&E staining revealed minimal superficial endothelial cell loss at the site of device activation, comparable to that observed in segments dilated with a balloon alone. No deep mural injury, necrosis, or medial dissection was detected. Elastin and collagen architecture remained preserved in all pulmonary arterial samples.

Representative micrographs confirmed:

Intact endothelium with focal superficial flattening but no denudation. Preserved internal elastic lamina. Absence of transmural inflammation or smooth muscle vacuolization. Valvular leaflets with maintained thickness and flexible elastin fibers.

6. Discussion

Our findings demonstrate that rotational mechanical thrombectomy using the Cleaner™ wire is histologically safe in both porcine venous and ovine pulmonary arterial models. In native venous tissue, the device did not produce endothelial denudation, medial injury, or valvular trauma across both standard (60s) and prolonged (120s) activation periods. These data are consistent with prior studies involving the jugular vein in sheep as well as the IVC in New Zealand white rabbits, which also showed preservation of vessel architecture and no stenosis following Cleaner deployment.

Importantly, the inclusion of a pulmonary arterial cohort adds to the translational relevance of this work. The pulmonary artery, like the ilio caval system, is thin-walled and highly

sensitive to mechanical injury. The fact that Cleaner-induced endothelial changes were limited to minor surface flattening, comparable to compliant balloon inflation, underscores the general atraumatic nature of the device.

Valvular Pathophysiology and Implications

These findings align with existing literature demonstrating early and irreversible venous valve damage following DVT. Inflammatory cytokines, leukocyte infiltration, and fibroblast activation lead to loss of leaflet compliance and eventual fibrosis. Studies by Meissner et al. and Lurie et al.[9] confirm that once these changes are established, restoration of physiologic valve function is exceedingly rare. As such, the objective of thrombectomy should shift from restoration to preservation of remaining valve function.

Our results support the hypothesis that early intervention with atraumatic mechanical devices may reduce long-term valvular deterioration. By rapidly clearing thrombus while sparing structural elements, RMT may help maintain venous hemodynamics and reduce the incidence of post-thrombotic syndrome as demonstrated in studies like the CLOUT registry. [10]

7. Conclusion

Rotational thrombectomy using the CleanerTM rotational sinusoidal wire demonstrated a high safety profile in both porcine femoral and ilio caval venous segments and ovine pulmonary arteries. Even with extended activation durations, the device did not cause histologically significant injury to the endothelium, medial wall, or venous valves. These findings may reinforce the role of the CleanerTM rotational thrombectomy system as a tissue-sparing modality in the management of venous thromboembolism, supporting its use in clinical settings where mechanical disruption of wall adherent thrombus may be deemed essential.

8. References

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Appendix A. Appendix

Figure A.1: Cleaner Thrombectomy

Figure A.2: Histology of 60 second sample showing no endothelial denuding or disruption.

Figure A.3: Cleaner in porcine test subject

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Figure A.4: Histology of 120 second sample showing no major loss of endothelium or tissue disruption of valve.